

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITIES FOR THE PREVENTION OF DEVIANT BEHAVIOR OF ADOLESCENTS

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Annotation: This article presents a generalization of scientific and practical knowledge on the issues of age-related characteristics of adolescent personality development, and examines the main approaches to defining deviant behavior, which are based on different understandings of the norm: sociological, biological and psychological. A modern consideration of the main conditions and causes of deviant behavior in adolescents is relevant.

Key words: teenage stage of development, deviant behavior, life meaning, value orientations, risk factor, socialization.

Introduction. The current stage of development of our society is characterized by a very changed socio-economic and political situation. This entails serious changes in beliefs, views, and ideological positions of both individuals and entire social groups [5]. Of particular importance is the formation of value orientations of the younger generation. It is influenced by the specific socio-economic situation in the country, the media, fiction, and, of course, the value orientations of reference individuals and groups [1, 2, 3].

Today there is no single point of view on the definition of deviant behavior and the degree of its pathology. There are different approaches to defining deviant behavior, which are based on different understandings of the norm, sociological, biological and psychological [4, 6, 7].

The sociological approach defines deviation as a deviation from generally accepted, average stereotypes of behavior and identifies two types of deviant behavior of a constructive and destructive nature [9].

Deviant behavior of a destructive nature is the commission by a person or group of people of social actions that deviate from the sociocultural expectations and norms that dominate in society, generally accepted rules. As a result, this approach identifies destructive (asocial) deviation only with criminal behavior, criminally punishable, prohibited by law, and is only one of the forms of this type of deviant behavior [8, 10, 11].

The biological approach assumes the existence of unfavorable physiological or anatomical features of the child's body that complicate his social adaptation - genetic, inherited [12, 15]. These may be mental development disorders, hearing and vision defects, physical defects, damage to the nervous system, psychophysiological, associated with the influence of psychophysiological stress on the human body, conflict situations, the chemical composition of the environment, new types of energy, leading to various somatic, allergic, toxic diseases, physiological, including speech defects, external unattractiveness, shortcomings of a person's constitutional and somatic make-up, which in most cases cause a negative attitude from others, which leads to a distortion of the child's system of interpersonal relationships among peers, the team [7, 13, 14].

The psychological approach examines deviant behavior in connection with intrapersonal conflict, destruction and self-destruction of the individual, blocking personal growth, as well as states of mental defects, degeneracy, dementia and psychopathy. The cause of deviations in the behavior and development of a child may be the insufficient formation of certain functional brain systems that ensure the development of higher mental functions (minimal brain dysfunction, attention deficit disorder, hyperactivity syndrome) [17, 19]. Deviations of this kind are considered within the framework of neurology and neuropsychology. However, in

many cases, unusual forms of behavior that differ from the average idea of the norm are associated with character or personality traits [16].

The socio-psychological approach explains the reasons influencing the emergence of deviant behavior [18]: deviant behavior is the result of a complex interaction of processes occurring in society and the human mind.

Thus, deviant behavior is a system of actions or individual actions that contradict the legal or moral norms accepted in society. Consequently, deviant is behavior that deviates from the norms and standards established by society, be it norms of mental health, law, culture, morality, as well as behavior that does not satisfy the social expectations of a given society in a specific period of time [18, 22].

The main conditions and causes of deviant behavior in adolescents usually include:

1. Individual psychological characteristics that contribute to the formation of behavioral deviations: violations in the emotional-volitional sphere. Such features, most often, if not pathological, are formed as a result of unsatisfactory, erroneous upbringing in the family, as a result of various kinds of violations of parent-child relationships [21].

2. Accentuations (overly pronounced individual traits) of a teenager's character as an extreme version of the norm, in which individual character traits of a teenager are excessively enhanced, while there is selective vulnerability to a certain kind of psychogenic influences with good and even increased resistance to others. Under a certain set of circumstances, such teenagers unexpectedly react differently than others to the phenomena of life around them and act inappropriately in a seemingly standard situation.

3. A rapidly occurring teenage crisis, the desire for adulthood against the background of contradictions in physiological and mental development (hence the inadequacy of reactions in relationships with others and the inconsistency in actions and deeds). Often the inappropriate, defiant behavior of minors in adolescence (which, in fact, is the norm at this age) as a result of the incorrect, illiterate response of parents, teachers and other adults is reinforced and rooted.

4. The negative impact of spontaneous group communication in the formation of the personality of adolescents. The main activity of teenagers is communication, although the majority of them do not know how to do this competently and constructively. It is also noteworthy that no one specifically teaches them to communicate competently and constructively, so the main sources of learning are family and “film” communication patterns.

5. Social and pedagogical reasons, among which family (parental) and school stand out. The inconsistency of intra-family communication and relationships in adolescence is especially acute in functionally insolvent families that do not fulfill or formally perform their leading function - raising a full-fledged person. These include criminal, conflict, pedagogically insolvent, pedagogically passive, anti-pedagogical families. But even in functional families, adolescence creates many problems, and their incorrect solution leads to deviations in the behavior of adolescents. The school, as a rule, picks up the mistakes of parents in interacting with teenagers and aggravates them, thereby perpetuating the deviant behavior of minors.

6. School maladjustment is also one of the reasons for the emergence of behavioral deviations, usually of an aggressive and socially passive nature. Pedagogical errors, especially in the early stages of education, give rise to psychosocial personality problems of a maladaptive nature, which, not being resolved at primary school age, become the basis for all kinds of deviations in the psychosocial development of minors and in adolescence sharply change the behavior of minors in a negative direction.

Thus, deviant behavior includes various actions of adolescents of an aggressive, antisocial, addictive nature (alcoholism, toxic and drug addiction), various offenses and such typical adolescent reactions as opposition, running away from home, grouping with peers. The latter forms are usually not pathological in nature and should disappear with adulthood [2, 7].

Thus, the fundamental priority in the problem of deviant adolescent behavior is the preventive direction in the activities of all structures, links, and specialists involved in solving it. It is known that the prevention of deviant behavior is associated with the need to identify risk factors, among which it is important to note, first of all, macrosocial and macroeconomic conditions:

- protracted economic crisis;
- drastic changes in the social structure of society;
- incomplete development of the legal framework;
- environmental and demographic disasters;
- active sociocultural intervention of the West and the East, determinant destruction of traditional social, cultural, behavioral stereotypes, loss of value guidelines and ideals, destruction of the spiritual integrity of the subject of life, frustration of basic human needs [6, 17]. Among the socio-pedagogical risk factors, it is important to note neglect, family and pedagogical neglect, which produce a conflict-prone consciousness and, in its extreme manifestations, a perverted perception of the world. Among the psychological factors, an important place in adolescence is occupied by adolescent behavioral reactions, emancipation, grouping with peers, hobbies, hobbies, and emerging sexual desires [4, 11].

The main motive of the adolescent at-risk group is precisely search activity, the desire to learn the immensity, as well as group opinion and group behavior. The involvement of adolescents in the risk group is also facilitated by a lack of awareness of normative development and distorted information about the effects of drugs and the consequences of their use.

An important point in preventive work is teaching a teenager skills that allow him to adequately respond to emerging ambiguous life situations on an intellectual basis, by assessing the situation and developing the main tendencies to overcome it. There is a stereotype of teachers towards teenagers:

- unchanged social status - a teenager is still a schoolchild;
- complete financial dependence on parents;

- the usual style of adults in education is to guide and control;
- preservation of childish traits in behavior.

It is important to discuss with teenagers the problem of the rights and responsibilities of each person, including parents, in relation to themselves. Therefore, the success of raising a teenager and preventing emerging deviant behavior largely depends on overcoming the stereotypical attitude towards a teenager as a child.

Conclusions. Thus, the effectiveness of psychological and pedagogical prevention of deviant behavior largely depends on socio-political, socio-economic, cultural and historical conditions and on the level of appropriate readiness of psychologists, teachers, their personal principles, value orientations, abilities and skills.

References:

1. Karimova, B. K., & Oripova, M. S. (2021). Formation of national pride based on hadiths in primary school children of houses of kindness. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(4), 652-665.
2. Karimova, B. (2019). Possibilities of formation of national pride with using khadiths in the first-year pupils of orphanages. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol*, 7(11).
3. Karimova, B. X. (2022). "Oilaviy bolalar uylari" boshlang'ich sinf yoshidagi tarbiyalanuvchilarida vatanparvarlik tuyg 'usini milliy g 'ururni shakllantirish asosida tarbiyalash. *Integration of science, education and practice. Scientific-methodical journal*, 3(9), 13-21.
4. Karimova, B. X. (2023). Ta'lim muassasasiga rahbarlik qilishning boshqaruv madaniyati. Pedagogik menejmentda kreativlik va kasbiy kompetensiyani shakllantirish. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(4), 918-924.
5. Karimova, B. X. (2023). Ta'lim muassasasiga rahbarlik qilishning boshqaruv madaniyati. Pedagogik menejmentda kreativlik va kasbiy kompetensiyani

shakllantirish. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(4), 918-924.

6. Karimova, B. X. (2021). Mehribonlik uylari boshlang'ich sinf tarbiyalanuvchilarida milliy g'ururni hadislar asosida shakllantirishning nazariy va amaliy ahamiyati. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(9), 952-961.

7. Khairullaevna, K. B. (2020). Content and criteria for formation of national pride in primary school pupils of orphanages. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol*, 8(7).

8. Khayrullayevna, K. B. (2022, November). Development of pedagogical skills in primary school teachers. In *Proceedings of International Conference on Modern Science and Scientific Studies* (Vol. 1, No. 2, pp. 170-174).

9. Shafoatovna, M. Z. (2021). Scientific and Theoretical Basis of Factors for Improving Family Education in a Multilingual Environment. *World Bulletin of Management and Law*, 1(1), 15-16.

10. Shafoatovna, M. Z. Factors That Improve Family Education in a Multilingual Environment. *International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology*, 55-57.

11. Shafoatovna, M. Z., & Muzaffar o'g'li, T. K. (2023, November). Pedagogik kompetentlik va keativlikni shakllantirish. In " USA" international scientific and practical conference topical issues of science (vol. 8, no. 1).

12. Shafoatovna, m. Z. (2023). In the family the child right brings up conditions. *Boshqaruv va etika qoidalari onlayn ilmiy jurnali*, 3(5), 158-160.

13. Mamaraimova, Z. S. (2023). Yuqori sinf o 'quvchilarini oilaviy hayotga tayyorlash jarayonining ijtimoiy-pedagogik xususiyatlari va omillari. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(4), 925-931.

14. Mamaraimova, Z. S. (2021). Ko'p tillilik muhitida oilaviy tarbiya munosabatlarini takomillashtirishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(9), 657-665.

15. Turdimurodov, D. (2024). Talabalarda jismoniy tarbiyaga bo'lgan motivatsiyani shakllantirish xususiyatlari. *Журнал «Вестник физической культуры и спорта» Нукусского филиала Узбекского государственного университета физической культуры и спорта, 1(2).*

16. Turdimurodov, D. (2024). Sportchilarning boksdagi texnik harakatlariga moslashish reaksiyalari. *Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари / Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук / Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences., 4(5).*

17. Turdimurodov, D. Y., & Safarova, F. (2024). Preparing future teachers for pedagogical communication as an adaptation factor. *World of Scientific news in Science, 2(4), 257-266.*

18. Каримова, Б. Х. (2019). Формирование национальной гордости у воспитанников 2 классов домов мехрибонлик на основе хадисов. In *European research: innovation in science, education and technology* (pp. 35-37).

19. Kh, K. B. (2019). Формирование чувства национальной гордости воспитанников начальных классов домов милосердия посредством хадисов. *International scientific review, (LXIV), 54-56.*

20. Маджидова, Д. А., & Мамараимова, З. Ш. (2013). Семья как важный фактор формирования здорового мировоззрения. *Молодой ученый, (5), 738-740.*

21. Мамараимова, З. (2023). Yuqori sinf o'quvchilarini oilaviy hayotga tayyorlashning pedagogik tamoyillari. *Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences., 3(12/2).*

22. Турдимуродов, Д. (2024). Sport mashg'ulotlari jarayonida pedagogik nazoratning ahamiyati. *Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences., 4(4).*